

Stig2Health: Stigma-directed services to improve ‘linkage to care’ for people living with HIV in rural Tanzania: study protocol for a nested pre-post implementation study within the Kilombero and Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort

Extended information for sample size calculation

Population: Eligible population is newly diagnosed, consenting adults (15+ years) enrolled in KIULARCO.

Primary outcome: Being in care and on ART treatment at 2 months (defined as having any visit [clinical, drug order, drug refill, or vitals form completed] between 1.5 – 4 months).

Based on the August 16th 2019 KIULARCO dataset and as per protocol

Pre-implementation period: Enrolled in 2018 (for purposes of the sample size calculation we used cohort data from the year 2018)

Implementation period: 01st Jan 2020 – 31st December 2020 (proposed)

Table 1: Numbers for Pre-implementation and post-implementation groups

Group	Pre-cohort 15+ years	Pre-cohort 15-45 years
Period year	2018	2018
Consented to KIULARCO	718	718
Adults 15+ years	637	
Adults 15-45 years		463
Exclude HIV diagnosis >7 days	-29	-23
Exclude prior ART	-97	-73
Newly diagnosed*	511	367
In care and on ART treatment at 2 months	346 (68%)	255 (70%)
	Post-cohort 15+ years	Post-cohort 15-45 years
Estimated sample size**		
10% increase from 70% - 80%	321	419
15% increase from 70% - 85%	98	106

*defined as HIV diagnosis within 7 days from enrolment into KIULARCO and no prior ART exposure.

** assuming a two-sided type I error rate of 5% and power of 90%

Primary outcome pre-implementation cohort: Among those newly enrolled consenting adults, 346/511 (68%) were in care and on ART treatment at 2 months in the pre-implementation cohort (Jan – Dec 2018). We expect a higher proportion of about 70% in 2019 since some stigma intervention activities have started.

Implementation group: A sample size of 321 newly diagnosed, consenting adults should be enrolled into KIULARCO to detect 10% increase in being in care and initiated ART treatment at 2 months (from 70% to 80%) assuming a two-sided type I error rate of 5% and power of 90%.

Text for the protocol (FV 6 sept 2021)

The sample size calculation was based on cohort data from 2018, when 511 adults were newly diagnosed and of whom 346 (68%) were in care and on ART at 2 months. Assuming a pre-implementation cohort of 511 adults, a 10% increase in linkage (from 70 to 80%), a two-sided type I error rate of 5%, and 90% power, 321 adults are required for the post-implementation group.

Appendix

```
. power twoproportions 0.7 0.8, test(chi2) power(0.9) n1(511) compute(n2)
```

Performing iteration ...

Estimated sample sizes for a two-sample proportions test

Pearson's chi-squared test

Ho: $p_2 = p_1$ versus Ha: $p_2 \neq p_1$

Study parameters:

```
alpha = 0.0500
power = 0.9000
delta = 0.1000 (difference)
p1 = 0.7000
p2 = 0.8000
N1 = 511
```

Estimated sample sizes:

```
N = 832
N2 = 321
```

```
. power twoproportions 0.7 0.8, n1(511) n2(321)
```

Estimated power for a two-sample proportions test

Pearson's chi-squared test

Ho: $p_2 = p_1$ versus Ha: $p_2 \neq p_1$

Study parameters:

alpha = 0.0500
N = 832
N1 = 511
N2 = 321
N2/N1 = 0.6282
delta = 0.1000 (difference)
p1 = 0.7000
p2 = 0.8000

Estimated power:

power = 0.9001